

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION
SCIENCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE-575001.

CERTIFICATE

Certified that this report entitled “..... **MUSIC LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**” is a bonafide record of project work done by **Mr.SACHIN V (USN.:3SU18CI023)**, towards the partial fulfilment of the requirements of the sixth semester Bachelor of Computer Application in Cloud technology and Information Security degree of Srinivas University during the academic year 2020- 21.

Livin M Miranda
Internal Guide

Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat B
Dean

Examiners

1. KUDPI VITTAL SHENOY

2. LIVIN M. MIRANDA

 Ujwal
 Livin M Miranda
4/8/21

DEAN
College of Computer Science & Information Science
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND
INFORMATION SCIENCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE-575001.

CERTIFICATE

Certified that this report entitled “ ALPHA MEDICALS” is a bonafide record of project work done by **Mr. Aldrin Flaxon Dsouza (3SU18CI004)**, towards the partial fulfilment of the requirements of the sixth semester Bachelor of Computer Application in Cloud technology and Information Security degree of Srinivas University during the academic year 2020- 21.

Vittal
Mr. Vittal Shenoy
Internal Guide

[Signature]
Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat B
Dean

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Examiners

1. SWATHI SHETTY *SH 3/8/21*

2. KUDPI VITTAL SHENOY *Vittal 3/8/21*

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PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE- 575001

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A
Final Project report

On

"ALPHA MEDICALS"

*Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of
Bachelor of Computer Application in Cloud Technology and
Information Security degree of Srinivas University.*

Submitted by

Mr. MOHAMMED ISHAM
USN: 38018CI016

Under the guidance of
Mr. Vittal Shenoy, MTech
Senior Faculty-IT Academics,
iNurture Education Solutions Pvt Ltd

2020-21

**COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND
INFORMATION SCIENCE SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY**

PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE-575001

SRINIVAS

UNIVERSITY

A PROJECT REPORT ON

“ WORK SPACE”

A project Report submitted to Srinivas University on partial Fulfilment sixth semester

Bachelor of computer Application degree

By

Shabaaz (2017BCASD022)

Under the guidance of

Dr. KRISHNA PRASAD K Associate professor

College of Computer Science & Information Sciences

Srinivas Institute of management studies

Pandeshwar, Mangalore

2017-2020

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(PRIVATE UNIVERSITY ESTABLISHED UNDER KARNATAKA STATE ACT NO.42 OF 2013)

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College of Computer Science and Information Science

Date: 03/09/2021

CERTIFICATE

This is to Certified that the project work entitled "**SCHOOL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**" carried out by **Mr. Ashish Krishna P. (Reg. No. 3SU18SA005)** a bonafide Student of this institution in partial fulfillment for the award of **Bachelor of Computer Applications** in Software Development of the SRINIVAS University, Mangaluru during the year 2018-2021. It is certified that all corrections/suggestions indicated for internal Assessment have been incorporated in the Report. The project report has been approved as it satisfies the academic requirements in respect of Project work prescribed for the said Degree.

CHAITRA D.S

Name & Signature
of the Guide

Name & Signature of
the HOD/Dean

External Viva

Name of the examiners

Signature with Date

1. MANGESH NAYAK

2. CHAITRA D.S

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

PANDESHWAR, MANGALORE- 575 001

A

Final Project report

On

"Pet Store Management"

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Computer Application in Cloud Technology and Information Security degree of Srinivas University.

Submitted by

MS DAKSHAYANI P.K

USN: 3S118CI005

Under the guidance of

Ms.Swathi Shetty, MCA

Faculty-IT Academics,

iNurture Education Solutions Pvt Ltd

2020-21

**COLLEGE OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION
SCIENCE, SRINIVASUNIVERSITY**

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